

Which Structural Constraints Are Learnable? A Regime Map for a Minecraft Voxel Generator

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Abstract

Neural procedural content generation (PCG) systems produce 3D game content, but practitioners lack guidance on which structural constraints their generator will enforce. We measure 14 structural properties of Minecraft buildings (32^3 voxel grids, ~ 260 block types) generated by a VQ-VAE + autoregressive transformer with classifier-free guidance. The properties separate into three regimes: **Controllable** (9 properties, $>100\%$ relative shift; 7 confident), **Approachable** (4, 20–100%), and **Unresponsive** (1, $<20\%$). The product of effective signal and training CV correlates with regime membership for emergent (not directly conditioned) properties (Spearman $\rho=0.879$, $p=0.002$, $n=10$); the small sample limits predictive generalization. Varying the guidance scale separates *representation ceilings* (requiring architectural changes) from *frequency floors* (addressable with more data), giving practitioners a diagnostic before expensive retraining.

Keywords

constraint learnability, controllability, procedural content generation, discrete generative models, VQ-VAE, autoregressive transformer, Minecraft

1 Introduction

A level designer wants towers to be tall and buildings to be symmetric, but which of these requests will the generator actually honor? Neural PCG systems based on discrete generative models now produce game levels [17] and 3D structures [7], yet control over their outputs is uneven. Some structural constraints respond to conditioning while others do not, even within the same model. Practitioners have no standard way to predict which constraints will fail before running experiments.

We ask: *given a neural PCG pipeline and a set of structural constraints, which constraints are learnable, and can we predict this from the training data alone?*

For example, conditioning on “tall building” reliably produces taller outputs, while conditioning on “hollow building” has negligible effect on hollowness, even though hollow structures exist in the training data. The usual fix is to add training data or tune hyperparameters, which assumes the failure is data-limited. But some constraints are bounded by what the decoder can represent, not by data scarcity. Whether the bottleneck is in the data or in the representation determines the right response: more data, or a different architecture.

We study this in Minecraft building generation (32^3 voxel grids, ~ 260 block types) using a VQ-VAE [20] + autoregressive transformer with classifier-free guidance (CFG), conditioned on six structural features (§3). The architecture has no constraint-specific inductive biases.

We make three contributions:

- (1) A **three-regime learnability map** across 14 structural properties with bootstrap 95% confidence intervals, classifying constraints as Controllable, Approachable, or Unresponsive (§4).
- (2) A **composite correlation** between two pre-experiment features (effective signal and training CV) and regime membership, with $\rho=+0.879$ (permutation $p=0.002$, $n=10$) for emergent properties, proposed as a hypothesis for future validation (§5).
- (3) A **dual bottleneck analysis** via CFG sensitivity, separating representation ceilings from frequency floors (§6).

2 Related Work

Discrete 3D generation. VoxelCNN [3] introduced autoregressive voxel generation on Minecraft structures from the 3D-Craft dataset. SAR3D [2] scales VQ-VAE + autoregressive generation to general 3D objects. Scaffold Diffusion [11] applies discrete diffusion to community-sourced Minecraft buildings. We use the same VQ-VAE + AR architecture but target learnability analysis rather than generation quality.

Controllable generation. MarioGPT [17] demonstrated text-conditioned level generation. DreamCraft [7] conditions Minecraft generation on user specifications; projected diffusion [4] enforces hard constraints at inference. Conditional GANs generate levels with explicit property targets [9, 14]. PCGRL [13] uses RL to satisfy constraints and analyzes which ones agents learn to enforce. These works engineer better control. We hold the mechanism fixed and ask which constraints respond.

Constraint satisfaction and expressive range. Other work enforces constraints *explicitly*: WaveFunctionCollapse [12] via constraint propagation, Sturgeon [5] via learned priors with explicit constraints, and answer-set programming [15] via logical specifications. These methods guarantee satisfaction but only for constraints expressible in their formal language. Our regime map characterizes where learned (implicit) control suffices and where explicit methods remain necessary. Smith and Whitehead [16] introduced expressive range analysis for unconditional generators. The regime map extends this idea to *conditional* generation by measuring responsiveness to conditioning signals and diagnosing the bottleneck (data vs. representation) when responsiveness is low. Quality-diversity methods [8] illuminate feature spaces via search, whereas the regime map identifies which dimensions a learned generator covers *without* search. The PCGML survey [18] catalogs learned generators without addressing which constraints they can learn. Search-based PCG [19] guarantees constraints by construction but trades diversity. Data-property effects on learnability have been studied in supervised [21] and reinforcement learning [6], but generative PCG models remain unexamined.

3 Method

3.1 Data

The dataset contains 10,310 Minecraft builds from three sources: 3D-Craft [3] (annotated human constructions), Minecraft Schematics Dataset [1] (community-sourced schematics), and additional community builds. Each build is cropped and padded to a 32^3 voxel grid with ~ 260 block types. The dataset covers houses, towers, and larger complexes, with natural class imbalance: symmetric structures make up only 3.9% and enclosed structures only 2.4% of the training set.

3.2 Architecture

A VQ-VAE [20] (3D conv, 2048-entry codebook, 256d codes, ~ 22 M params) compresses 32^3 grids to 8^3 latent codes over 100K training steps; all 2048 codebook entries are active across the training set. An autoregressive transformer (512d, 12 layers, 8 heads, ~ 55 M params) generates the 512 latent codes in raster-scan order with 3D sinusoidal positional encodings. The transformer is trained for 80K steps (batch size 32, learning rate 2×10^{-4} , cosine decay). Raster-scan order means each token can attend only to spatially preceding positions; spatially adjacent but sequentially later tokens are invisible, which limits the model’s ability to coordinate global properties such as symmetry.

3.3 Structural Conditioning

Six discrete structural features (height, size, footprint, symmetry, enclosure, and complexity—a block-type diversity measure) are each embedded as a separate prefix token prepended to the autoregressive sequence. Classifier-free guidance (CFG) [10] drops all conditioning with 10% probability during training; at inference, unconditional and conditional logits ℓ_u, ℓ_c are interpolated as $\hat{\ell} = \ell_u + s(\ell_c - \ell_u)$ with guidance scale s (default 2).

3.4 Evaluation Protocol

Training-data statistics (effective signal, coefficient of variation (CV)) are computed from all 10,310 training builds. For each of seven conditioning configurations (unconditioned plus six targeted conditions), 40 samples are generated (5 seeds \times 8 per seed) and 14 structural properties are measured on each output. **Controllability** is $\text{ctrl}(p) = \max_{c \in C} |\mu_{p,c} - \mu_{p,\emptyset}| / \max(|\mu_{p,\emptyset}|, \epsilon)$, where $\mu_{p,c}$ is the mean of property p under condition c and $\mu_{p,\emptyset}$ is the unconditional mean ($\epsilon=0.001$ prevents division by zero). Bootstrap 95% CIs use 10,000 replicates resampled from the 40 samples per condition. Regime thresholds: $>100\% \rightarrow$ Controllable, $20\text{--}100\% \rightarrow$ Approachable, $<20\% \rightarrow$ Unresponsive; stable across 5 seeds.

4 Regime Map

The 14 properties span local (height, block count, bbox volume), semi-local (vertical aspect ratio, surface ratio, floor count, elongation, hollowness, layer consistency, footprint convexity), and global scales (symmetry IoU, Z-axis symmetry IoU, enclosure ratio, connected components). Of the six conditioning features (§3.3), four have a direct property counterpart (height, n_blocks via size, symmetry_iou via symmetry, enclosed_ratio via enclosure); footprint and complexity affect multiple properties but lack a one-to-one

Table 1: Constraint learnability regime map (CFG scale $s=2$, 5 seeds \times 8 samples per condition). Dir.: has a conditioning token. Eff.: effective signal (target-class frequency for direct; max proxy correlation for emergent). CV: training coefficient of variation. Ctrl%: max controllability with bootstrap 95% CI.

Property	Dir.	Eff.	CV	Ctrl% [95% CI]	Regime
<i>Controllable (>100% shift)</i>					
height	✓	.068	0.60	266 [197, 360]	C*
n_blocks	✓	.117	1.03	632 [394, 1050]	C*
symmetry_iou	✓	.039	1.33	237 [122, 492]	C*
enclosed_ratio [†]	✓	.024	5.37	564 [132, 1141]	C
floor_count		.765	0.76	182 [116, 269]	C*
bbox_volume		.750	1.03	422 [251, 725]	C*
connected_comp. [‡]		.090	1.44	128 [58, 233]	C
vertical_aspect		.784	0.61	333 [245, 446]	C*
z_symmetry_iou		.469	0.93	324 [161, 753]	C*
<i>Approachable (20–100% shift)</i>					
elongation		.179	1.76	64 [29, 105]	A
surface_ratio		.400	0.08	32 [27, 37]	A*
layer_consist.		.320	0.39	44 [29, 62]	A*
fp_convexity		.437	0.37	51 [34, 71]	A*
<i>Unresponsive (<20% shift)</i>					
hollowness		.311	0.23	14 [8, 19.9]	U*

*Regime assignment is *confident*: 95% CI lies entirely within one regime (enclosed_ratio excluded; see [†]).

[†]enclosed_ratio: percentage inflated by near-zero baseline ($\mu_0=0.00003$); absolute shift is only ~ 0.006 . Per-seed controllability ranges from 73% to 1119% (SD $\approx 462\%$); classification unreliable.

[‡]CI spans the C/A boundary; classified by point estimate (see text).

mapping. The remaining 10 properties are emergent, responding only through correlation with conditioned features.

Observations. All four directly conditioned properties are Controllable ($n=4$, insufficient to generalize). Five emergent properties also reach Controllable through proxy correlation alone; connected_comp. is borderline (CI spans the C/A boundary). The largest cross-axis transfer is z_symmetry_iou (+324%): X-axis symmetry conditioning increases Z-axis symmetry by over 3 \times , likely driven by correlated training data (symmetric builds tend to be symmetric on both axes), though partial preservation of symmetry in the latent space cannot be ruled out.

The single Unresponsive property (hollowness, 14% [8%, 19.9%]) has moderate proxy correlation (0.31) but very low training CV (0.23): the training set lacks sufficient variation along this axis for the model to learn a responsive representation.

Robustness. Regime assignments are stable across 5 random seeds. Varying boundaries from (10%, 80%) to (30%, 120%) changes at most one assignment. Under CI-conservative classification, 11 properties are confidently assigned (7 Controllable, 3 Approachable, 1 Unresponsive); 3 remain borderline: enclosed_ratio (CI above 100% but unreliable due to near-zero baseline), connected_comp. (CI [58%, 233%] spans C/A), and elongation (CI [29%, 105%] spans A/C).

Figure 1: Composite score (proxy corr. \times min(CV, 1)) vs. controllability ($n=10$ emergent properties). Neither proxy correlation ($\rho=0.624$, permutation $p=0.060$) nor CV ($\rho=0.636$, $p=0.053$) alone reaches significance; their product does ($\rho=0.879$, $p=0.002$).

5 Predictive Framework

We test whether regime membership *correlates* with features computable from training data alone, as a hypothesis for future validation on other architectures:

- **Effective signal:** For directly conditioned properties, the target-class frequency in training data. For emergent properties, the maximum absolute Pearson correlation with any conditioned property (proxy correlation).
- **Training CV:** The coefficient of variation of the property across the training distribution, measuring how much variation the model has opportunity to learn.

5.1 Direct Conditioning

All four directly conditioned properties are Controllable despite a $\sim 5\times$ range in training frequency (2.4%–11.7%), consistent with CFG amplification compensating for low frequency. However, $n=4$ with zero negative cases is too small to generalize (rule-of-three 95% upper bound on failure rate: $3/n=75\%$). `enclosed_ratio` (564%) reflects a near-zero baseline ($\mu=0.00003$; absolute shift ≈ 0.006 ; see Table 1 footnote).

5.2 Emergent Property Predictor

For the 10 emergent properties, controllability requires both proxy correlation *and* sufficient training CV. A composite score, signal \times min(CV, 1), captures this interaction (Figure 1; Spearman ρ ; controllability values permuted among properties, 10,000 replicates):

We pre-specified three formulations (CV alone, proxy correlation alone, and their product); only the composite reaches significance under permutation testing ($p=0.002$; Bonferroni-adjusted $p=0.005$ across three tests). Post hoc, alternative composites give comparable results: signal \times CV ($\rho=0.915$) and signal \times log(1+CV) ($\rho=0.879$); we report min(CV, 1) as the most conservative variant (lowest ρ , capping high-CV outliers). At $n=10$, we cannot reliably distinguish between these formulations. The 95% CI on $\rho=0.879$ at $n=10$ is approximately [0.55, 0.97], compatible with either a moderate or strong relationship. The interaction is multiplicative: a property

Table 2: CFG sensitivity (3 seeds \times 8 samples, 4 conditions). Controllability (%) at three guidance scales. Bold: only observed regime transition. § Approachable in Table 1.

Property	$s=0$	$s=2$	$s=4$	Pattern
height	132	224	240	C \rightarrow C
n_blocks	243	569	603	C \rightarrow C
symmetry_iou	149	190	242	C \rightarrow C
enclosed_ratio	158	542	328	C \rightarrow C
floor_count	88	167	197	A\rightarrowC
elongation	37	40	30	A \rightarrow A
connected_comp.	57	94	75	A \rightarrow A
layer_consist.	24	31	38	A \rightarrow A
fp_convexity	26	45	52	A \rightarrow A
hollowness	6	12	19	U \rightarrow U
surface_ratio [§]	13	15	14	U \rightarrow U

Note: Fewer seeds (3 vs. 5) and conditions (4 vs. 7) than Table 1; three Controllable emergent properties omitted for space. Values at $s=2$ are not directly comparable due to different seeds and condition subsets. `surface_ratio` appears Unresponsive here (15%) but Approachable (32%) in Table 1 because the condition driving its best shift is absent.

needs both a correlation pathway (high proxy correlation) and sufficient training CV for the model to learn from. Hollowness (proxy correlation 0.31, CV 0.23) illustrates the interaction: moderate proxy correlation but too little training CV. Connected components (proxy correlation 0.09, CV 1.44) have the opposite profile: high training CV but almost no correlation pathway.

A discrete decision tree achieves 90% training accuracy on the 10 emergent properties but only 60% three-class LOO accuracy (6/10 correct; majority-class baseline 50%), as expected at this sample size. The continuous correlation is the primary result.

6 Dual Bottleneck Analysis

The regime map shows *that* some properties are unresponsive, but not *why*. Two explanations are possible: (a) insufficient signal from the conditioning pathway (**frequency floor**), or (b) the decoder cannot express the constraint (**representation ceiling**).

These are distinguished by varying the CFG scale ($s \in \{0, 2, 4\}$, where $s=0$ reduces to unconditional generation) at inference without retraining. A frequency-limited property should amplify with stronger guidance; a representation-limited one should not.

Table 2 shows three patterns. *Weak amplification:* hollowness responds monotonically (6%, 12%, 19% at $s=0, 2, 4$) but stays below 20%; whether stronger guidance would cross the threshold remains untested. `surface_ratio` shows negligible response (13%, 15%, 14%). *Frequency floor:* `floor_count` crosses from A to C (88%, 167%, 197%). `enclosed_ratio` responds non-monotonically (158%, 542%, 328%), possibly due to CFG distortion [10]. *Stable Approachable:* the remaining properties stay within 20–100% across all guidance scales.

The `floor_count` transition suggests that some frequency-floor constraints may respond to stronger guidance, though only one such case was observed. Representation-ceiling constraints require changes to the decoder or latent space. Figure 2 illustrates the amplification effect.

Figure 2: CFG sensitivity at scales $s=0, 2, 4$. Enclosure conditioning responds to amplification (frequency floor). Height at $s=0$ produces fragmented outputs; at $s=4$, conditioning is stronger but block-type diversity decreases.

7 Discussion and Conclusion

Implications for practitioners. For **Controllable** properties, standard CFG conditioning suffices. **Approachable** properties (frequency floor) benefit from data augmentation, stronger CFG, or targeted fine-tuning. **Unresponsive** properties may require changes to the decoder or latent space, or practitioners can layer explicit constraint methods [4, 12, 19] on top of the learned generator.

Limitations. (1) Single architecture and dataset. The methodology may generalize, but only this pipeline has been tested; specific coefficients will differ on other architectures. (2) $n=10$ emergent properties is small. The composite ($\rho=0.879$, $CI \approx [0.55, 0.97]$) is a hypothesis, not a validated predictor. (3) Zero negative cases for direct conditioning ($n=4$). (4) Percentage shifts mislead for near-zero baselines (enclosed_ratio: 564% but only 0.006 absolute). Regime assignments near boundaries depend on which conditions are tested (surface_ratio: Approachable with 7 conditions, Unresponsive with 4). (5) The 40 per-condition samples are clustered within 5 seeds (8 per seed); the bootstrap resamples individual samples, which may understate variance if within-seed correlation is high.

Conclusion. In this pipeline, constraint learnability is well-predicted by the product of effective signal and training CV ($\rho=0.879$, $p=0.002$); generalization to other pipelines remains untested. For PCG practitioners, the dual bottleneck analysis separates frequency floors from representation ceilings, informing whether to collect more data or redesign the architecture. These results are from a single VQ-VAE + AR pipeline on Minecraft data. The diagnostic *methodology* (regime map construction, CFG sensitivity sweep) is what we intend to be transferable; validation on other architectures (e.g., diffusion-based PCG) and non-voxel domains is needed to confirm generality.

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A Sample Outputs

Figure 3 shows representative outputs under each conditioning type at the default guidance scale ($s=2$), alongside unconditioned

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baselines. Each row corresponds to one condition; four random samples are shown per row. The visual differences illustrate the regime map: height and size produce clearly distinct outputs (Controllable),

while enclosure conditioning yields structures that remain largely open (near-zero baseline).

Structural Constraint Controllability: Unconditioned vs Conditioned Samples

Figure 3: Generated samples across five conditions. Rows (top to bottom): unconditioned, height=tower, size=large, symmetry=1, enclosure=1. Four samples per condition at guidance scale $s=2$. Isometric voxel rendering; 32^3 grids, ~ 260 block types.